

Restoring Trust in US Elections through Effective Election Administrator Messaging

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Abstract

During the 2020 election cycle, numerous national, state, and local organizations mounted campaigns designed to counter mis- and disinformation about election activities and to foster public trust in election processes. Local and state election offices focused intently on creating and disseminating accurate messages about when, where, and how to vote. Despite these efforts, trust in the 2020 election remained confoundingly low. This research analyzes this disconnect between messages from election offices and public trust by testing messages collected from election officials around the country using focus groups and a national panel survey experiment. We find that in focus groups, neutral messages that evoke local connections tested better than other types of messages. Further, messenger characteristics influenced whether participants trusted the messages. Using messages based on these findings, we fielded a survey experiment during the 2022 midterm election cycle, finding that the interaction between baseline trust, racial identification, and identification with the messenger moves trust.

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The 2020 presidential election underscored the potential for political messaging to be used to undermine the public's trust in elections and election administration. Messaging suggested or directly stated that election results have been rigged, that results should not be trusted, or that election officials themselves were somehow complicit. The foundation of American democracy is the trust citizens have in the democratic process: that if they vote and are eligible, their vote is counted as intended. Political messaging designed to erode that trust in order to manipulate public opinion threatens the integrity of the system.

However, the news is not all bad. Extant research suggests messaging can enhance citizen trust in electoral processes. In this article, we describe research in which we worked with local election officials (LEOs) to test their existing public messaging related to trust in election processes and administration. LEOs are the primary points of contact for information about the processes of registering to vote, casting ballots, and counting results; in order to register and vote, the public must engage in processes and procedures with their local election office. We used a three-pronged approach. We first leveraged partnerships with local election officials to examine existing messages. We then conducted focus groups about these messages with citizens across the country interested in elections. Finally, we tested the efficacy of the most effective messages, identified by the focus groups, using a national survey and an experimental approach.

We found, in focus groups, that neutral messages that evoke local connections resonated the most in building trust. Further, messenger characteristics influenced whether participants trusted messages, particularly partisanship and race. In a survey experiment, we found that the interaction between a respondent's baseline trust (before receiving a message), their racial identification, and the representativeness of the messenger moved trust. Respondents who identify as Black and had low initial trust in elections can be moved by neutral, factual appeals, especially if the messenger is symbolically representative. White respondents are more uniform in their responses, with low initial trusters responding positively to almost all messages, but with smaller marginal effects. To our knowledge, no systematic empirical research has been conducted about trust in communications from LEOs. To provide a foundation for our research, we draw upon diverse literature that reflects analysis of trust from various institutional and behavioral vantage points.

Defining, Measuring, and Understanding Trust

Defining trust is complicated (Craig, Niemi, and Silver 1990), and moving it even more so. At the individual level, psychologists argue that it is a “brain process”—physical, psychological, and emotional—that considers the self, others, contextual factors, and feelings as part of a neural pattern that influences decision-making (Thagard 2018). At the collective level, the concept is sometimes referred to as social trust, which is thought of as “a measure of how people evaluate the moral fabric in their society” (Rothstein and Uslaner 2005, p. 43). Trust generally correlates with “a positive view of their democratic institutions, to participate more in politics, and to be more active in civic organizations,” as well as greater charitable giving and greater tolerance of out-groups, more personal optimism, and greater happiness (Rothstein and Uslaner 2005, p. 41).

The Psychological Foundations of Trust (and Distrust)

Trust is also influenced by personal traits and limits to human cognition, which influence when we trust and when we do not. The combination of motivated reasoning, confirmation bias, bias blindspot, and in-group and affinity bias shapes how we process information, and these limitations have been exacerbated by the current political and media environment. With respect to trust, the implications of motivated reasoning are especially pronounced. We tend to believe information that confirms what we want to believe—we find arguments that support our existing beliefs more compelling than those that contradict what we want to be true (Kunda 1990; Miller, Saunders, and Farhart 2016; Kenski 2017; Christensen and Moynihan 2020). We also seek out information that confirms our prior beliefs, and we highlight that information unconsciously when we make judgements and decisions. Like motivated reasoning, confirmation bias means that humans prefer new information that confirms what we already believe (Nickerson 1998; McKenzie 2006). Countering confirmation bias requires putting into place deliberate processes to force us to examine disconfirming information, like absorbing contradictory messaging. Prior beliefs or attitudes are therefore difficult to change.

These processes work together to make implicit bias, which drives affinity and in-group bias, more pernicious. Implicit bias is a function of “unconscious mental processes in nondeliberate discriminatory behavior” (Jones 2017, p. 1222). Greater levels of trust are related to greater levels of tolerance for out-groups (Uslaner 2004; Uslaner and Brown 2005). Flipping this on its head, out-group members are likely to have lower levels of trust in institutions at baseline because they regularly face implicit bias at the individual, institutional, and structural levels. Countering this distrust then requires adapting strategies to lift up common fates and sameness, using messengers who can relay this by either accentuating sameness and in-group bias or dampening out-group effects (Gaertner and Dovidio 2000). Psychologists sometimes refer to these related forms of bias as bias blind spot (Pronin, Lin, and Ross 2002; McPherson Frantz 2006; Pronin 2007, 2008; Scopelliti et al. 2015; Bessarabova et al. 2016). We believe ourselves to be objective and that we understand the world around us accurately, so it is incredibly difficult for us to identify or locate our own biases.

In thinking about what has driven trust in government and elections to lower levels in the 2020 election than in previous elections, we might consider the impact of so-called interpretation bias (Bockstaele et al. 2020). Looking at competing explanations, people with predispositions may fixate on the more negative explanation to the exclusion of more positive or even benign explanations. This is particularly true when people are anxious or afraid (which may be influenced by more vulnerability) and for people who

have low levels of tolerance for uncertainty. This form of bias is also self-reinforcing. Being anxious about a situation triggers a preference for the more negative explanation, and in turn that new belief leads to greater depression or anxiety, and in some cases to more aggressive behavior. These processes are exacerbated when political elites claim that there is fraud in elections, even when those claims are unsubstantiated (Justwan and Williamson 2022).

Consider the collection of conspiracy theories that were promulgated through the 2020 election cycle. Some of these included: that the Democratic Party runs child-trafficking rings; that the Deep State is part of Satan worship; that Trump really won the election and is secretly running the government from Florida while Biden is just a prop (who will later be arrested); and that voting systems were rigged to change votes from Trump to Biden. Many of the psychological mechanisms that characterize human cognition make some people more likely to believe in these types of conspiracy theories than others. Motivated reasoning for people who are highly knowledgeable about politics but also lack trust in government operates to make them more inclined to believe in conspiracy theories (Miller, Saunders, and Farhart 2016). This is particularly true when someone's side is losing or has lost. These effects are likely exacerbated when trusted political leaders espouse these theories (Berlinski et al. 2023).

Since 2016, misinformation (the spread of false or incorrect information without malice) and disinformation (the spread of the same kind of information with the intent to deceive or mislead with malice) now characterizes the electoral environment. The goal of disinformation campaigns is to damage and destabilize enemies by driving wedges between adversarial groups or to misdirect their attention and resources. Part of what makes them successful is that the false information is based, at least in part, on reality or the perception of reality. The disinformation campaigns leading to the 2016 presidential election were characterized by troll farms focused on increasing social cleavages through social media, hacking and releasing confidential emails of centralized political campaign committees (e.g., the DCCC), phishing campaigns targeting vendors, probing of election offices' electronic systems, and intrusion into some statewide voter registration databases. They were effective because of social media: social media is easy to exploit because of the "low barrier to entry and ease of sharing user-generated content" (Hui 2020 and because it allows for an increase in "traditional political mudslinging ... through rumours [sic], half-truths or completely fabricated information" (p. 156). These conditions work together to make the public ripe to be primed by influence campaigns, especially when political leaders espouse the same unsubstantiated claims (Berlinski et al. 2023).

Trust in Government and Elections

These individual-level mechanisms and the mis- and disinformation environment of elections can be used to understand overall trust in government and its officials, including LEOs. Changes in trust in government often occur around elections: elections trigger changes in trust in government based on the outcome of the election, and people trust government more when their candidate or party wins. Trust in elections themselves depends upon whether your side was the winner or loser—at the presidential level, this effect grows during the first year of an administration and peaks in the second year, and the effect is higher when there is a partisan change of power. In 2020, this effect was larger than for most other elections (i.e., the losing side’s drop in trust doubled compared with what typically happens when someone’s candidate does not win) (Pew Research Center 2022).

That Republican trust in the 2020 election results was low after the election is consistent with our understanding that trust in government generally declines when the candidate of a party loyalist is losing or has lost. The greater the political competition, the greater the gulf is likely to be between those who trust the results of an election and those who do not (Carlin and Love 2018). However, trust in local government offices (the locus of most election activity and citizen interaction) is generally high. In the 2020 election cycle, the barrage of questions, concerns, and even threats that local election officials received was likely a function of the normal effect of losing plus perhaps some role confusion—with LEOs seen by some as a function of national government operations rather than as representatives of local government and local communities.

Research Expectations and Hypotheses

Trust in government is thus a complex process, and because of the nature of human cognition is not easily changed. However, maximizing trust is important; as Hetherington (1998, p. 791) states, “low trust helps create a political environment in which it is more difficult for leaders to succeed.” Levi and Stoker (2000, p. 501) conclude that trust impacts whether citizens “become politically active, how they vote, whether they favor policy or institutional reforms, whether they comply with political authorities, and whether they trust one another.” The intentional deployment of disinformation campaigns to destabilize the country has had the effect of exacerbating partisan fighting, which has essentially produced two concurrent and opposed realities among the public. This in turn has deepened distrust in elections and election administration, necessitating effective messaging from LEOs to restore citizen attitudes toward the work they do.

Attempts to counter mis- and disinformation and to rebuild trust in the process by election officials is difficult, but not impossible. Simple messages that evoke a collective orientation, in part by reminding people of a shared fate through messages focused on the local level where trust is already greater, should elicit a more positive response by helping mitigate against bias blind spot and motivated reasoning. Trusted messengers may also mediate the effects of mis- and disinformation by promoting in-group and affinity bias. Given this, we expect the following:

Research Expectation 1: Connecting election administration to local, known, relatable officials will produce a higher sense of trust among weak distrusters;

Research Expectation 2: Simple messages evoking positive emotional responses (patriotism, humor, etc.) will produce a higher sense of trust among weak distrusters; and

Research Expectation 3: No strategy will be effective for moving trust among those at the extreme ends of the trust spectrum.

Methodology

Our research comes in three stages. In the first stage, we worked with election officials over two years (2020-2021) to collect different types of messages they were using to communicate with the public.¹ These were call scripts responding to phone calls, communications provided by vendors, and social media platforms, and included memes, tweets, and short, office-created videos. We categorized the messages into three types: (1) factual messages (i.e., dates and times of elections, rules, etc.), (2) factual messages with humor, and (3) factual messages with an emotional overlay. We were also able to organize these messages by messenger into the following types: (1) no explicit messenger, (2) an election official or expert who is generally identifiable as such, and (3) someone who claims to be an election official or expert but without much public familiarity. Although the messages from the election administration community generally grew in sophistication over the two-year period, election officials tended to focus messages solely on facts—dates, locations, and processes. Larger local election jurisdictions (i.e., larger counties) tended to have greater sophistication and interest in generating memes and videos to capture public attention, as did some of the state offices.

During the same time, a plethora of other groups in the online environment were messaging to counter disinformation. The US Election Assistance Commission staff and commissioners produced some messaging, as did related groups like the National Association of Secretaries of State (NASS)

¹Our work was informed by a research advisory working group of volunteer members from the Election Center (or National Association of Election Officials).

and National Association of State Election Directors (NASED). One notable effort was the #trustedinfo2020 campaign, a hashtag designed to be included with messages to inform the public that the message came from a credible source. We collected messages from these groups as well. Together, these formed the corpus of messages explored in the focus groups, the results of which were used to design the national survey.

Focus Groups

In the second stage of our research, we worked with local election officials across the country to recruit Zoom-based focus groups through election office social media platforms in the spring of 2022. Local election officials used their social media accounts to encourage local citizens to participate, and those interested signed up for the focus groups online and were grouped based upon availability. Our hope was to recruit regular community members interested in elections as well as election deniers and people with doubts about the outcome of the 2020 election. However, by the time our recruitment messages were distributed, many of the people in the latter group had already moved to alternative social media platforms. Over 150 people responded to the focus group advertisements in which we offered \$75 to take an online survey (a pilot of the survey used in the later national panels) and to spend 90 minutes in the focus groups. In total, we held five focus groups, which included between four and thirteen people per group.² While we solicited voters generally and were clear to exclude active election officials, many of the volunteers had a deep interest in elections.

Among the final participants we interviewed, most were white, female, and over fifty years of age (and had an approximate age range of 20-75). The participants came from California, Florida, Iowa, Minnesota, Missouri, Nebraska, Nevada, New York, Texas, and Utah. In total, we spoke with thirty-one people we deemed met the criteria for inclusion in the study. Although we did not ask about political beliefs or ideology in the focus groups, participant answers suggested that they were primarily moderate to liberal. Three former election officials were included, as were people from election-adjacent groups (i.e., poll workers, politicians, and campaign staff). We did not screen participants in advance to create homogeneous groups on any characteristic; groups were formed on the basis of availability. We followed advice about running focus groups using online platforms to increase participation and reduce distractions (see, for example, Poliandri et al. 2023

²We experienced some attrition and had to remove a sizeable group of the pool, as we discovered through the first focus group that some participants claiming to meet our criteria (US citizens over 18 years of age) were in fact not US citizens and had used spoofed IP addresses to sign up.

or Santhosh, Rojas, and Lyons 2021). The focus groups were led by one of our team members, and each was attended by two other team members who took notes. We also recorded the focus groups and used those videos and transcripts for analysis. We varied the questioning parts of the focus group by calling on people as well as having them volunteer to speak. Some people were more talkative than others, so the focus group leader used prescribed follow-up questions to encourage participation from the less forthcoming participants to elicit greater information and feedback.

We began each focus group with a discussion of trust in government generally and trust in elections more specifically. We then ran through a series of messages gathered during stage one. These messages came in different forms (i.e., memes, tweets, quotes), and in one focus group we also included a series of “I Voted” stickers. We included several neutral, factual messages (some with messengers and some without), messages with positive and emotional appeals, messages with partisan power appeals, and clever messages using images and turns of phrase from popular culture. Examples are shown in Supplementary Material section A.

Focus Group Findings

The summary of the results across all the groups are found in table 1. In short, neutral messages tested more positively overall, especially the message that evoked familiarity and in-group affiliation (election officials are your neighbors). Messages that were overly clever or targeted to particular groups (whether intended or not) were almost universally rejected by participants. These messages were positively received when the participants shared and understood the cultural references evoked in these messages, but when there was any confusion, these messages immediately lost participant interest or, in the case of the “Cure” message (see Supplementary Material section A), evoked a strongly negative response.

In addition to response to message content, we were interested in response to messenger. In the community of election officials, there are some people, primarily because of their positions, who are universally known. We tested a few of these people as messengers, including Matthew Masterson, former US Election Assistance Commission (EAC) Republican commissioner who became well known because he was targeted by then President Trump for defending the integrity of the existing system, as well as Thomas Hicks, a long-standing EAC Democratic commissioner. Among the public, none of the participants had heard of these people, and when their role in elections was described, their federal affiliation lowered the group’s sense of trust and connection. We also discussed the #trustedinfo campaign initiative by NASS to promote accurate information on election administration; almost universally the hashtag message reduced participants’ trust, with some commenting

Table 1: Summary of Focus Group Findings

Message type	Example	Response trends
Neutral	“Did you know: one in five people eligible to vote has a disability? Nothing should prevent you from casting your ballot! You and your Vote matters! #RegisterToVote #GoVote”	Generally accepting Some questions about validity of the information
Neutral + messenger	Same messages as above Attribution: ACLU	Fear that folks will doubt the veracity of the claims because connected to a left-leaning organization
Neutral + messenger	“We have paper ballots. We looked at the paper ballots. The result was accurate.” Attribution: Matthew Masterson	Message seemed reasonable No idea who Masterson is or why they should believe him [after being told] Government affiliation problematic
Neutral + neighbors	“Election workers are your neighbors, teachers, aunts, grandparents, students—they come from all walks of life and participate in democracy. If you haven’t cast your ballot, and plan to vote in person on Tuesday, thank the election workers when you cast your ballot.” Attribution: Thomas Hicks	Universally positive response Many said “I will thank the election workers next time I vote” Several felt that all candidates and parties should repeat this leading up to elections
Positive/patriotic appeal	“Regardless of who holds the highest office in our grateful nation, it is our duty as American citizens to vote.” Attribution: Leonora Peters Gant	Mixed response Some agreed Some thought it was condescending, talked down to

Table 1: Continued.

Message type	Example	Response trends
Partisan power appeal ^a	“You can’t complain about the leadership if you don’t exercise your right to vote.”	Largely negative response Seemed too negative and discouraging
Clever/humorous appeal ^a	“Things that are better when cured: Salami; 80s music; your ballot.” Attribution: Arapahoe Votes “#VoterID is the law in Iowa. Every voter will be asked to show ID at the polls on Tuesday. Jedi mind tricks won’t help you. Make sure you’re #VoterReady. Voterready.Iowa.gov.” Attribution: Paul Pate	Only the election officials understood the content Only people who were teens in the 1980s got the band reference in the image Universally negative responses Greater understanding of reference More positive responses Some people misunderstood message because they read the caption on the picture first
#	#TrustedInfo	Almost none of the participants had heard about this campaign (the one election official had) Almost all had a negative response—the message triggered less trust, not more

^a Images associated with these messages are included in Supplementary Material section A.

that being told they should trust the source automatically drove a distrusting response. There were some exceptions to this. First, when the hashtag was paired with their state's Secretary of State, the response was positive, but only if the participant shared their party identification. Second, attitudes improved when the hashtag was associated with a local election official.

Finally, we tested a partisan power appeal message: that for your side to win, you had to go out and vote. The response to this message was largely negative. When pushed, the participants who did not like it largely could not explain why, just that it did not sit well with them. However, the messenger in this instance was a Black male, and our sense was that this reaction may be driven by implicit bias, as many of these negative responses came from older white women. We explored this reaction further by explicitly varying the race of the messenger in the next stage.

Overall, from these focus group findings, neutral messages (as opposed to the other message types in table 1) were the most effective at increasing trust. Given the unexpected response to the partisan power appeal message in the focus groups (where some participants seemed to resist a messenger who was not symbolically representative of them), we designed a survey experiment with different neutral messages delivered by two different messengers: a middle-aged white female to represent most LEOs (Adona 2019), and a similarly aged Black male.

National Survey

In our third stage, we fielded a survey experiment on a national sample through Qualtrics from October 26, 2022, to November 4, 2022. Following our research expectations and focus group learning, we designed a 4 x 2 experimental manipulation with one control condition. Our treatment of interest is a hypothetical message from an LEO. Since many local election offices are on Twitter, we replicated a hypothetical tweet from an LEO, varying the content of the message as well as the messenger. Each respondent viewed exactly one tweet while taking the survey.

The first manipulation was the message that each respondent received. Given our focus group findings about the efficacy of neutral messages, each survey taker was exposed to one of four possible neutral messages. Each message was crafted to reflect actual content disseminated by local election offices through the 2022 midterm election. The information (i.e., the years of experience of the average election worker) is accurate with respect to real-life LEOs. The messages span four categories

1. Civic duty: "Voting is the foundation of democracy, and the cornerstone of this foundation is the election worker who spends their life working as hard as possible to ensure your right to vote in a free and

fair election. The next time you vote, trust and thank the worker who keeps your rights safe and protects democracy.”

2. Experience: “Did you know: the average election worker has over 15 years of experience processing registrations, administering polling places, and counting ballots? They are experts: so when you’re wondering who to trust for election information, trust the people who do it all day, every day.”
3. Neighbor: “Election workers are your neighbors, teachers, aunts, grandparents, students—they come from all walks of life and participate in our democracy. If you haven’t cast your ballot, and plan to vote in person on Tuesday, thank the election workers when you cast your ballot.”
4. Rules: “Elections are guided by a system of rules issued by your legislature: rules about what ballots can be used, when they can be cast, how they are counted, and who is eligible to receive them. Even if you don’t like the rules, trust the election worker. Their job is to follow the rules.”

These four message manipulations were paired with two different messengers: a Black male (named “Tom Jackson”) and a white female (named “Sarah Brown”). Both messengers are fictional.³ The name of the messenger was noted as the author of the tweet, and a picture of the messenger was shown as their avatar. To hold as much else constant as possible between the tweets, each works for the “Johnson Co. Board of Elections,” each has a blue checkmark, and each tweets from “@RedBlueAmerica.” The tweets were “sent” at the same time and on the same date; retweets and comments were hidden to encourage respondents to focus on the message.⁴ A control condition was also included that displayed a message about fast food. Examples of the tweets are shown in figure 1. The generic nature of the individual messages gives us confidence that no survey respondent likely viewed the messenger as their own “local” election official.

Our dependent variables of interest are whether an individual trusts an LEO in three key areas:

1. How much do you trust local election officials to do their part ensuring a free and fair election?

³The images used for both people are actual government employees. The white female is a state official who works in a state government office in health care who gave permission for her image to be used, and the Black male image is Thomas Hicks, an EAC commissioner, used with his permission. See figure 1 for the pictures used.

⁴In a manipulation check, 100 percent of the respondents recalled the author of the tweet, suggesting a strong ingestion of the treatment.

- Control Message:
@RedBlueAmerica
- Just tried the "improved" fries at Wendy's. Can't say I'm that impressed.
- 2:57 PM · Sep 13, 2022
-
-
- Civic Duty:
@RedBlueAmerica
- Voting is the foundation of democracy, and the cornerstone of this foundation is the election worker who spends their life working as hard as possible to ensure your right to vote in a free and fair election. The next time you vote, trust and thank the worker who keeps your rights safe and protects democracy.
- 2:57 PM · Sep 13, 2022
-
-
- Experience:
@RedBlueAmerica
- Did you know: the average election worker has over 15 years of experience processing registrations, administering polling places, and counting ballots? They are experts: so when you're wondering who to trust for election information, trust the people who do it all day, every day.
- 2:57 PM · Sep 13, 2022
-
-
- Neighbors:
@RedBlueAmerica
- Election workers are your neighbors, teachers, aunts, grandparents, students--they come from all walks of life and participate in our democracy. If you haven't cast your ballot, and plan to vote in person on Tuesday, thank the election workers when you cast your ballot.
- 2:57 PM · Sep 13, 2022
-
-
- Rule Followers:
@RedBlueAmerica
- Elections are guided by a system of rules issued by your legislature: rules about what ballots can be used, when they can be cast, how they are counted, and who is eligible to receive them. Even if you don't like the rules, trust the election worker. Their job is to follow the rules.
- 2:57 PM · Sep 13, 2022
-
-

Figure 1: Tweets from Experimental Manipulation

2. To what extent do you trust local election officials to follow the rules of election law?
3. To what extent do you believe elections are run by ethical people?

Respondents were invited to select on a five-point scale, ranging from “None at all,” “A little,” “A moderate amount,” and “A lot,” to “A great deal” (or “Unsure/Prefer not to respond”). These measures were fielded before and after the treatment, allowing us to calculate the change in each dimension of trust for each individual. After adjusting for incomplete and inattentive responses (listwise deletion), we were left with an unweighted sample of 4,019. Each passed multiple attention checks: one about the author of the experimental manipulation, the other instructing respondents to select a specific multiple-choice response.

Figure 2 explores the considerable baseline variation in trust in LEOs by plotting the density of baseline (pretreatment) trust in elections as an additive index, faceted by respondent racial identification. Since each trust question ranges from 1 to 5, the lowest possible level of combined initial trust is 3, and the highest initial trust is 15. Higher levels of initial trust suggest ceiling effects, as trust cannot be improved. Since our messenger manipulation features a white female or Black male messenger, we draw attention to the baseline trust in these groups. Black identifiers are centered in roughly the middle of the scale, with a strong tail (higher trust) toward the right. There is considerable trust among white individuals, with the peak of the distribution at the highest possible level of trust (so a large portion of this group will be subject to ceiling effects).

National Survey Findings

We begin by checking for main effects from the experimental manipulation. Table 2 shows the results of three regressions. The dependent variables are the changes in levels of trust in our three dimensions (compared to the control): LEOs running free and fair elections, following the rules of election law, and whether they are ethical people.

The results can be quickly summarized: hardly any of the experimental conditions have any substantively significant effects. No experimental condition is successful in raising the perception that LEOs administer free and fair elections. Only two experimental conditions—the experience and civic duty of LEOs from a Black male messenger—raise the perception that LEOs follow rules or are ethical people. Even then, these effects are muted (0.128 points; $p = 0.044$) on a five-point scale. The perception that LEOs are ethical likewise increases by 0.228 points ($p = 0.001$) in the Black male messenger, experience condition—6 percent of the scale—and 0.159 points ($p = 0.008$) in the Black male messenger, civic duty condition—4 percent of the scale.

Figure 2: Baseline Variation in Trust by Racial Identification.

These muted effects might give cause for concern to LEOs. However, recall that we expect these treatment effects might be heterogeneous by initial trust in elections and whether the messenger was symbolically representative. Table 2 ignores this heterogeneity, so perhaps it is unsurprising that we observe no effect of the manipulation. Instead, we turn to whether the treatment effects are heterogeneous by symbolic representation with the messenger or levels of baseline trust in elections. To explore this potential interaction between race, preexisting trust, and the treatments, we estimated three separate models. Again, the three dependent variables are the changes in an individual’s level of trust in LEOs on our three key dimensions: if LEOs conduct free and fair elections, if they follow rules, and if they are ethical. The core of each is a triple interaction between the concepts of interest—the treatment received, the individual’s baseline of initial trust,⁵

⁵For ease of interpretation, we define a “low truster” as those in the bottom quartile of baseline trust in elections (from figure 2).

Table 1: Regression Results: Predicted Changes in Trust from Experimental Treatments.

Experimental condition	Change in belief that local election officials are ...		
	Free and fair	Follow rules	Ethical
Black duty	0.006 (0.059) [0.916]	0.074 (0.064) [0.247]	0.159 (0.059) [0.008]
Black experience	0.056 (0.063) [0.340]	0.128 (0.059) [0.044]	0.228 (0.059) [0.001]
Black neighbor	-0.045 (0.060) [0.454]	0.019 (0.065) [0.769]	0.069 (0.061) [0.256]
Black rules	-0.064 (0.060) [0.290]	0.042 (0.065) [0.512]	0.008 (0.061) [0.899]
White duty	-0.076 (0.060) [0.204]	-0.010 (0.064) [0.878]	-0.015 (0.060) [0.804]
White experience	-0.043 (0.060) [0.477]	0.048 (0.065) [0.454]	0.061 (0.060) [0.310]
White neighbor	-0.043 (0.060) [0.477]	0.014 (0.065) [0.823]	0.079 (0.061) [0.192]
White rules	-0.038 (0.059) [0.522]	0.001 (0.064) [0.982]	0.064 (0.060) [0.289]
Constant	0.036 (0.043) [0.404]	-0.017 (0.046) [0.718]	-0.129 (0.043) [0.003]
Observations	4,019	4,019	4,019
Adjusted R^2	0.00001	-0.00001	0.005

Note: Standard errors in parentheses; exact p -values in brackets.

and the individual's racial identification. We control for political interest, individual party identification, self-placed ideology, income, whether they voted in 2020, education, age, political knowledge, gender, and level of conspiratorial thinking.

These models produce an inscrutable number of coefficients (9 treatments x 3 racial identifications x 2 levels of trust). Accordingly, we plot the change

in the level of trust after reading a particular message versus the corresponding change in the control group: a “difference-in-differences” estimator.⁶ In each of the next three plots, the experimental condition is shown along the x-axis. The y-axis is the predicted change in trust in the modeled dimension for the corresponding treatment and group, with 95 percent confidence intervals around the estimate. High initial trusters are shown in gray; low initial trusters are shown in black. Finally, racial identification is indicated by plot character, where circles represent “other” (not white or Black, for which we have no strong hypotheses), triangles represent Black, and squares represent white racial identifiers. Note for each model that the estimates are much more precise for white individuals than for Black individuals, given their different sample sizes.⁷

Beginning with figure 3, the change in trust in whether LEOs run free and fair elections, the estimates for low initial trusters respond universally more positively than high initial trusters. Among Black individuals, the most effective treatment for increasing trust is the Black male messenger, experience message. Black low initial trusters show an increase in trust in LEOs providing a free and fair election by about 1.5 points, which is an incredible 37 percent of the scale of the measure (five-point scale). Even Black high initial trusters (the gray triangle) have a statistically significant increase in their trust, which is the only statistically significant positive treatment among any group of high initial trusters in figure 3. The other treatments are also effective, but less so, among Black low initial trusters (ranging from just over one-point increases for the Black male messenger, civic duty message to a 0.6 increase in the Black male messenger, follow rules message). This same effect does not exist when Black low trusters receive messages from white female messengers. Only two treatments—white female messenger, civic duty message and white female messenger, follow rules message—are significant, and their estimated effects (0.9 and 0.8) are muted by comparison. Interestingly, Black low trusters respond more to the following rules treatment from a white female messenger versus a Black male messenger (the last column), suggesting an increase in trust after learning that rules constrain white LEOs. Finally, the reactions of Black high initial trusters to the white female messenger, experience message and white female messenger, civic duty message are negative, suggesting a backfire effect to messaging from LEOs who are not symbolically representative when focusing on these dimensions.

⁶For each, we hold political interest, party identification, ideology, income, education, and conspiratorial thinking at their means. We hold voting status at voter, gender at male, and explore the effects for someone who is not politically knowledgeable.

⁷The sample sizes of each group are in Supplementary Material section D.

Figure 3: Difference-in-difference estimation for whether local election officials ensure free and fair elections (versus control) by racial identification and baseline trust.

The same patterns do not appear for white low initial trusters. Almost all the estimates are centered near 0.6, regardless of message or messenger. The highest estimate is for Black male messenger, follow rules message (about 0.7), and the lowest estimate is for Black male messenger, civic duty message (about 0.5). Interestingly, high initial trusters (gray squares) are also centered around the same space; however, these estimates are negative. This is likely the ceiling effects discussed above.

Figure 4 shifts attention to the change in trust related to whether LEOs follow rules. The general pattern of estimates is relatively consistent when compared to figure 3, which is exceptional. We would have expected that a treatment tailored to the rule-following nature of election administration (either the experience message or the follow rules message) would be effective especially on this dimension. It's not that it is ineffective: for Black

Figure 4: Difference-in-difference estimation for whether local election officials follow rules (versus control) by racial identification and baseline trust.

individuals, the Black male messenger, experience message treatment is successful, but the effect looks like figure 3 and the free and fair dimension (that is, the message performs well for both dimensions of trust). Both the Black male messenger, civic duty message and Black male messenger, neighbor messages are roughly equally effective (about a one-point increase). For Black initial low trusters, the white female messenger, civic duty message and white female messenger, neighbor message treatments are effective, though less effective than any other condition from a symbolically representative messenger (other than Black male messenger, follow rules message). White female messenger, both experience and follow rules messages are insignificant, with the former estimated at almost exactly zero.

The story is relatively similar for white low initial trusters as it was in figure 3 for free and fair elections, with two exceptions. First, the treatment effects are all muted. Whereas the treatment effects are centered at about 0.6

Figure 5: Difference-in-difference estimation for whether local election officials are ethical (versus control) by racial identification and baseline trust.

in figure 3, in figure 4 (for follow rules) the estimates trend around 0.5. Our treatments, then, are less effective at convincing white low trusters that LEOs follow rules than they are that LEOs administer free and fair elections. The exception is the Black male messenger, follow rules message, which is estimated at 0.8. White individuals are more likely to trust that LEOs follow rules when they are assured that Black LEOs follow them.

Figure 5 explores the final remaining dimension of trust: whether LEOs are ethical. For Black low initial trusters (black triangles), the story is different. Three treatments, all from symbolically representative messengers, are quite effective. With estimates ranging from 1.0 to 1.5, the Black male messenger, civic duty message, follow rules message, and experience message all significantly improve trust among Black low initial trusters. However, the Black male messenger, neighbor message does nothing to convince Black low initial trusters that LEOs are ethical. Moreover, only one message

from a white female messenger—civic duty—is effective, although the estimate is weaker than any of the successful Black male messages. No other message from a white female messenger—experience, neighbor, or follow rules—moves trust. When it comes to trust in ethics, then, Black low trusters react to messages from symbolically representative messengers. (All the estimates for Black high initial trusters overlap with zero, suggesting that there is no effect for Black high initial trusters.)

Again, the story is relatively similar for white initial low trusters (black squares). This time, though, the estimates are centered even lower: the point estimates for all treatments (but one) are centered below 0.5. The exception is the Black male messenger, civic duty message, which is estimated to be almost twice as effective (0.6 versus 0.3) as the white female messenger, civic duty message. For white high initial trusters, though, there is a backfire effect. Showing individuals who already believed that LEOs were to be trusted makes them skeptical of the ethics of LEOs.

We get strong evidence for our suspected interaction between baseline trust, racial identification, and symbolic representation. Black individuals with low baseline levels of trust in elections respond most to messages from Black male messengers, though the most effective message depends on the dimension of trust in question (free and fair, following rules, or ethical). Black individuals with low baseline levels of trust in elections are skeptical or even resistant to messages from white female messengers. Black individuals with high baseline trust in elections are still willing to improve that trust when shown messages from Black male messengers, but this turns negative when shown messages from white female messengers.

White individuals are far more uniform. Although the average value of the estimate changes across each dimension—highest for free and fair elections, lowest for ethical—white individuals with low initial trust in elections react positively and consistently by improving their trust, regardless of messenger or message. This improvement is smaller than the improvement achieved among Black low initial trusters. But the messages are effective, even if minimally. For white high initial trusters, though, these messages run into ceiling effects, as individuals who are already predisposed to trusting elections (recall figure 2) become skeptical about being told to trust a group that they already trusted.

Conclusions

Trust in government is complex and not easily changed. In an environment characterized by disinformation campaigns to destabilize the country and demonize LEOs for unsubstantiated widespread fraud, trust in election administration is even more complex. This heated political environment has exacerbated partisan fighting and deepened distrust. The purpose of this

research is to help uncover tools that LEOs may be able to use to counter these problems.

Using messages developed by election officials, we tested these tools in two ways. National focus groups found that simple, neutral, factual messages that lifted up election officials as neighbors (and were thus relatable and evoked a sense of sameness and a collective orientation) resonated with respondents. Other types of messages evoking patriotism and humor tested less well. Representative messengers also mattered. Taking these findings, we then developed a series of four neutral messages evoking civic duty, professionalism and experience, neighbors and connections, and officials as rule followers. We found that among initial high trusters, the messages did not move results, as they were subject to ceiling effects. However, among lower trusters these messages moved trust for all participants, especially if the messenger was symbolically representative. Message and messenger matter.

We get mixed evidence, then, for Research Expectation 1. Messages that emphasize the LEO as known (i.e., experienced) or relatable (i.e., a neighbor) resonate when received by a symbolically represented low-truster, but the pattern across dimensions of trust (administering free and fair elections, following rules, or being ethical) is not clear. Our focus groups severely discount Research Expectation 2, as messages with emotional appeals tend to be viewed skeptically and with imputed partisanship, if they are viewed at all. We also reject Research Expectation 3; instead of performing worst among strong distrusters, our experimental messages actually perform best at restoring trust in elections among those with low initial trust.

Since 2016, the study of election administration and the role of subnational governments in election processes has expanded considerably, while floods of mis- and disinformation clogged virtually every means of public communication about the election process. Public trust in election operations has suffered dramatically, and repairing it will take time and effort on multiple fronts. One heartening conclusion here is identifying at least a few messaging paths that election administration professionals can utilize which can enhance the likelihood of making and maintaining positive connections with the public that they serve. Election officials have agency within the limits of law to fight against the pernicious environment in which they find themselves, and messaging to voters is a low-cost and potentially effective way to do this.

Supplementary Material

Supplementary Material may be found in the online version of this article:
<https://doi.org/10.1093/poq/nfae033>.

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Data Availability

Replication data and documentation will be available within 12 months of publication at <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/BKSITS>.

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